

ADAPTED OCAP[®] PRINCIPLES

DATASHEET FOR INDIGENOUS DATASETS

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DATASET IDENTIFICATION

1. Dataset title
2. Brief description of dataset contents
3. Primary language(s) represented
4. Time period covered

MOTIVATION & PURPOSE

1. Why was this dataset created?
2. What goals does this dataset serve?
3. How does this dataset support self-determination?

CREATION AND FUNDING

1. Who funded the creation of this dataset?
2. How will sustainability of the dataset be funded and for how long?

COMMUNITY APPROVAL

1. Who is the primary community representative?
2. When is the next scheduled review date and process?

OWNERSHIP

1. Which Indigenous community owns this dataset?
2. Who created the dataset?
3. What community members, knowledge holders, or cultural authorities were involved?
4. How are individual vs. collective ownership rights balanced?
5. What consent and approval processes were followed?

CONTROL

1. Who has decision-making authority over this data? (council, elders, traditional authorities, data stewards)
2. What approval processes must external users follow?
3. How can the community modify or revoke permissions?
4. How is cultural responsiveness and accuracy ensured throughout data management?

ACCESS

1. What are the different access levels? (e.g., community-only, restricted, research, public)
2. How is access controlled?
3. How do external parties request access and what criteria guide access?
4. What are approved purposes and what uses are explicitly prohibited?
5. How can consent be modified or revoked?

POSSESSION

1. Where is the data physically and digitally housed?
2. What is the format of the dataset?
3. What technical processing was done and who was involved? Who oversaw this process?
4. How does the community maintain control over copies and backups of the dataset?